

DERLA, MOISES JR. O. Central Bicol State University of Agriculture, Pili, Camarines Sur. April 2017. **DISASTER RISK REDUCTION MANAGEMENT AND CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTATION OF BROADCAST MEDIA IN NAGA CITY.**

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This study measured the effectiveness and capability of the selected radio stations and broadcast journalists in Naga City along Disaster Risk Reduction Management and Climate Change Adaptation. The effectiveness and capability of the subject radio stations and broadcast journalists were measured through the feedbacks gathered in four areas in Naga City and Camarines Sur representing the urban, lowland, upland and coastal areas. This study also measured the capacity and effectiveness of the respondent radio stations based on their equipment, budget, signal power and number of personnel while the respondents broadcast journalists were measured based on their education, experience in radio industry, age and seminars attended regarding DRRM and CCA.

The author discussed the effectiveness and capability of the selected radio stations and broadcast journalists in Naga City as to how they created public awareness using the airplane. The researcher is very positive that this study will help the broadcast journalist in Naga City and their respective networks to equip their stations and people of knowledge and skills on Disaster Risk Reduction Management and Climate Change Adaptation.